

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION OF THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: Within the framework of this article, the authors attempt to study the specifics of teaching karakalpak language in the context of digitalization. To do this, first of all, an analysis of the current economic, social, political and cultural situation is carried out. On its basis, the need for further measures related to the integration of information and telecommunication technologies into the process of teaching students a karakalpak language is proven. Next, they give an essential characteristic of the concept of “digitalization of education.” A distinction is made between it and the definition of “informatization of education.” The main aspects of digitalization are discussed, including in relation to language training.

Then the didactic potential of information and communication technologies is identified. The most essential pedagogical conditions are determined that can contribute to their most effective use in the course of developing karakalpak language competencies among individuals studying in modern higher education organizations operating on the territory of the Karakalpakistan.

Key words: Higher education, karakalpak language at a university, karakalpak language at a non-linguistic university, informatization of education, digitalization of education.

Accordingly, its goal is to study the specifics of teaching karakalpak language in the context of digitalization.

- give an essential description of the concept of “digitalization of education”;
- identify the didactic potential of information and communication technologies;

In addition, their competent use can significantly increase the variety of educational content. Opportunities for productive interaction between subjects of educational relations using modern telecommunications are expanding. All this means building a virtual authentic language environment. Blended learning, thus, makes it possible to optimize the process of students learning a karakalpak language. This is achieved through the effective organization of independent

activities of students, providing for a harmonious combination of innovative and traditional educational technologies. Based on the above, we can see that the stage of informatization of the Karakalpak Higher Education system has now been successfully completed. Currently, we are talking about the need to create a digital educational environment. In this regard, the concept of “digitalization” is more applicable. The latter can be considered in the following aspects: widespread use of digital technologies in teaching karakalpak language to students and telecommunications; a method of manipulating information necessary in the educational process using digital devices; in-depth computerization of educational systems, various forms of educational and extracurricular activities, carried out in order to further improve them and ensure greater accessibility for all subjects of educational relations. The key aspects of digitalization of the modern system of domestic HE can be considered the expansion of the influence of the Internet and mobile communications on the course of the educational process, which becomes especially relevant in the existing sociocultural conditions. Their use can significantly facilitate access to karakalpak language sources of information and various options for using the language being studied. In addition, competent use of the opportunities provided by digitalization can significantly increase the variety of educational content.

In the digital age, several digital resources have been created with the aim of promoting the preservation and use of the Karakalpak language. Some examples include: there are online dictionaries that show translations, definitions and examples of words in Karakalpak language. These dictionaries help Karakalpak speakers to easily search for words and phrases, enhancing their language skills and understanding.

The process of productive interaction between subjects of educational relations is optimized using modern tools telecommunications. All this means building a virtual authentic language environment.

Taking into account the undeniable advantages inherent in these and other digital means of developing karakalpak language competencies, it should be remembered that they cannot and should not completely replace the teacher in the corresponding process.

Their widespread implementation only makes it possible to generate pedagogical conditions for the more effective implementation of some components of karakalpak language activities in a creative form. In this regard, the implementation of so-called “blended learning” seems to be the most

promising. This term means the combined use of the most effective traditional and innovative forms of organizing the educational process when learning a karakalpak language. Guided by the requirements of the new stage of development of the educational system, the main measures are aimed at improving the system of continuous education, providing it with modern technologies, and strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions. Holding sports competitions, competitions, and school Olympiads on a large scale contributes to the comprehensive development of schoolchildren and their admission to universities without competitive exams. Thus, the implementation of the National Personnel Training Program has become a new stage in the development and renewal of our society. The program, which has no analogues in the world, is already producing positive results.

In educational institutions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, with close cooperation, the necessary organizational, psychological, pedagogical, methodological conditions are created for the implementation of the goals and objectives of public education in accordance with the National Personnel Training Program.

Our article is devoted to concretizing this influence. Thus, today we are talking about the need to create a digital educational environment. The concept of “digitalization” is more applicable here. This last one can be considered in the following aspects:

- to determine pedagogical conditions that contribute to their most effective use in the course of developing karakalpak language competencies among individuals studying in modern Higher Education organizations.

- language

The following tasks correlate with the goal:

- a method of manipulating information necessary in the educational process using digital devices;

- in-depth computerization of educational systems, various forms of educational and extracurricular activities, carried out in order to further improve them and ensure greater accessibility for all subjects of educational relations. Based on the above, it becomes obvious that the key aspects of digitalization of the modern system of domestic Higher Education can be considered the expansion of the influence of the Internet and mobile communications on the course of the educational process. Modern ICTs

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significantly facilitate access to karakalpak language sources of information and various options for using the language being studied.

- widespread use of digital technologies and telecommunications in teaching karakalpak language to students;

The goals of general secondary education are: the formation of knowledge and skills in students in accordance with state educational standards, general culture, their adaptation to life in society, the development of independent thinking, the ability to make informed choices and readiness to continue their studies at an academic lyceum or vocational college, the education of a well-rounded personality - a citizen, the formation of a sense of patriotism, devotion to the principles of independence and democracy. The latter can be designated by the term “digitalization”.

The penetration of information and communication technologies (ICT) into all spheres of life of human society has contributed to their significant transformation. This process could not but influence the development of the higher education system, in particular the language training of students

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